

DETERMINANTAL REPRESENTATIONS OF SOME CLASSICAL RECURRENT SEQUENCES

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Abstract

In this paper, we find multi-sum expressions for several second-order recurrent sequences including the Fibonacci, Lucas, Pell, and Jacobsthal numbers. These expressions may also be written equivalently as Toeplitz–Hessenberg determinant identities involving the Oresme numbers. We obtain these formulas as special cases of more general results for the Horadam numbers involving a class of determinants and their associated generating functions. We also find a criterion for determining when a generic Horadam sequence can be expressed explicitly as a determinant of a Toeplitz–Hessenberg matrix with associated sequence $a_i = (bi + c)d^i$ for $i \geq 1$. Finally, we provide combinatorial proofs of several of our identities for the Fibonacci numbers and others, wherein we enumerate certain structures featuring $(m+r)$ -color compositions of n for various r .

1. Introduction

We first recall some well-known combinatorial sequences. The Fibonacci, Lucas, Pell, Pell–Lucas, and Jacobsthal number sequences are denoted by F_n , L_n , P_n , Q_n , and J_n and are given, respectively, as follows for $n \geq 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} F_n &: F_0 = 0, F_1 = 1 \text{ and } F_n = F_{n-1} + F_{n-2}, \\ L_n &: L_0 = 2, L_1 = 1 \text{ and } L_n = L_{n-1} + L_{n-2}, \\ P_n &: P_0 = 0, P_1 = 1 \text{ and } P_n = 2P_{n-1} + P_{n-2}, \\ Q_n &: Q_0 = Q_1 = 2 \text{ and } Q_n = 2Q_{n-1} + Q_{n-2}, \end{aligned}$$

$$J_n : J_0 = 0, J_1 = 1 \text{ and } J_n = J_{n-1} + 2J_{n-2},$$

where each recurrence applies for all $n \geq 2$. See, respectively, entries A000045, A000032, A000129, A002203, and A001045 in the OEIS [16] for further information on these sequences.

In [11], the following multi-sum expressions were obtained for the Fibonacci and Pell numbers.

Proposition 1. *For $n \geq 1$, the following formulas hold:*

$$F_{2n} = \sum_{\substack{s_1, \dots, s_n \geq 0 \\ s_1 + 2s_2 + \dots + ns_n = n}} m_n(s) 1^{s_1} 2^{s_2} \dots n^{s_n}, \tag{1}$$

$$F_{3n-1} = 2^{n-1} \cdot \sum_{\substack{s_1, \dots, s_n \geq 0 \\ s_1 + 2s_2 + \dots + ns_n = n}} m_n(s) \left(\frac{1}{1}\right)^{s_1} \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{s_2} \dots \left(\frac{2n-1}{2^{n-1}}\right)^{s_n}, \tag{2}$$

$$P_{n-1} = 2^{n-1} \cdot \sum_{\substack{s_1, \dots, s_{n-1} \geq 0 \\ 2s_1 + 3s_2 + \dots + ns_{n-1} = n}} m_{n-1}(s) \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{s_1} \left(\frac{2}{4}\right)^{s_2} \dots \left(\frac{n-1}{2^{n-1}}\right)^{s_{n-1}}, \tag{3}$$

where $m_n(s) = \binom{s_1 + \dots + s_n}{s_1, \dots, s_n} = \frac{(s_1 + \dots + s_n)!}{s_1! \dots s_n!}$.

In this paper, we extend these results by finding some further identities involving F_n and P_n as well as formulas for L_n , Q_n , and J_n . We remark that these formulas can be obtained as special cases of more general results involving the Horadam sequence. Let $O_n = \frac{n}{2^n}$, $n \geq 0$, denote the n -th Oresme number, which is given recursively by $O_n = O_{n-1} - \frac{1}{4}O_{n-2}$, $n \geq 2$, with $O_0 = 0$ and $O_1 = \frac{1}{2}$. We refer the reader to [6, 13] for further properties of O_n . It will be seen that our multi-sum formulas for the sequences above may be expressed as determinants of certain Toeplitz–Hessenberg matrices with Oresme number entries (see Corollary 4 below). Other recent results have been given for Toeplitz–Hessenberg matrices whose nonzero entries are derived from various combinatorial sequences, among them, the Catalan [7], Fibonacci [8], Motzkin [9], and Leonardo [10] numbers.

Let $v_n = v_n(p, q, r, s)$ denote the n -th Horadam number (see, e.g., [12]) defined recursively by $v_n = rv_{n-1} + sv_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 2$, with $v_0 = p$ and $v_1 = q$, where p, q, r, s are variables. We will determine a general explicit formula (Theorem 1) in terms of determinants for v_n whose parameters satisfy a certain restriction. We consider further the special case of v_n when $r = s = 1$, known as the *Gibonacci* numbers, which will be denoted here by G_n as in [4]. That is, the numbers G_n satisfy the recursion $G_n = G_{n-1} + G_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 2$, with $G_0 = p$ and $G_1 = q$. Note that G_n reduces to F_n and L_n when $(p, q) = (0, 1)$ and $(2, 1)$, respectively.

The organization of this paper is as follows. In the next section, we find explicit determinantal expressions for several specific second-order recurrent sequences as

well as a general formula for a class of Horadam sequences. Formulas in these specific cases are subsequently expressed equivalently as Oresme number determinant identities. In the third section, we establish a determinantal expression for the sequence kG_{n+m} for $n \geq 1$, where k is a constant (dependent upon m , G_0 , and G_1) and $m \geq 0$ is fixed, which is subsequently generalized (Theorems 2 and 3). Further, it is shown that among all sequences of the form $F_{\ell n+m}$ for $n \geq 0$, where $\ell \geq 1$ and $m \geq 0$ are fixed, only the sequences F_{n+3} and F_{2n} admit an expression as a determinant of a Toeplitz–Hessenberg matrix with associated sequence $a_i = (bi + c)d^i$ for $i \geq 1$ (see Proposition 2).

In the final section, we provide combinatorial arguments of several of our multi-sum formulas utilizing structures that incorporate $(m + r)$ -color compositions as well as certain types of square-and-domino tilings. We prove our results by direct enumeration, either in establishing a defining recurrence relation or providing a bijection between some pertinent discrete structures. In one case, a result is proven by first defining a suitable sign-changing involution and then enumerating the set of survivors of the involution. Recall that the number of $(m + 1)$ - and $(m + 3)$ -color compositions of n are given by $A003480(n)$ and $A010908(n - 1)$, respectively. As a consequence of our arguments for (11) and (14) in the last section, we obtain, via combinatorial proofs, new formulas for these sequences as follows:

$$A003480(n) = \begin{cases} 2^{(n-1)/2}P_{n+1}, & n \text{ odd;} \\ 2^{(n-4)/2}Q_{n+1}, & n \text{ even,} \end{cases}$$

and $A010908(n) = 2^{n-1}F_{2n+6}$ for $n \geq 1$. We remark that different expressions for these sequences were found in [5] which involve a double summation.

2. Determinantal Representations of Recurrent Sequences

An $n \times n$ matrix A_n of the form

$$A_n := A_n(a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n) = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ a_2 & a_1 & a_0 & \cdots & 0 & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \ddots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n-1} & a_{n-2} & a_{n-3} & \cdots & a_1 & a_0 \\ a_n & a_{n-1} & a_{n-2} & \cdots & a_2 & a_1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $a_0 \neq 0$, is said to be *Toeplitz–Hessenberg* (see, e.g., [15]). The determinant of A_n is given explicitly in terms of the a_i as follows.

Lemma 1. *If $n \geq 1$, then*

$$\det(A_n) = \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} (-a_0)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) a_1^{\alpha_1} a_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots a_n^{\alpha_n}, \quad (5)$$

where the sum is over all n -tuples $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$ of non-negative integers such that $\tilde{\alpha} = \alpha_1 + 2\alpha_2 + \dots + n\alpha_n = n$, with $|\alpha| = \alpha_1 + \dots + \alpha_n$ and $m_n(\alpha) = \frac{|\alpha|!}{\alpha_1! \dots \alpha_n!}$.

The preceding result is known as *Trudi's formula* [14, Theorem 1], the $a_0 = 1$ case of which has been attributed to Brioschi [15].

Define the generating functions

$$f(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \det(A_n)x^n \quad \text{and} \quad g(x) = \sum_{i \geq 1} a_i x^i,$$

where A_n is of the form in (4). Using (5), one can show the following relation between $f(x)$ and $g(x)$, see [10].

Lemma 2. *We have*

$$f(x) = \frac{-\frac{1}{a_0}g(-a_0x)}{1 + \frac{1}{a_0}g(-a_0x)}. \tag{6}$$

Given $n \geq 1$ and indeterminates a, b, c , and d , let $U_n = U_n(a, b, c, d)$ be the $n \times n$ Toeplitz–Hessenberg matrix wherein $a_0 = a$ and $a_i = (bi + c)d^i$ for $i \geq 1$. Let $u_n = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ denote the determinant of the matrix U_n for $n \geq 1$.

Remark 1. Even though one may take $d = 1$ in u_n without loss of generality, due to the easily verified relation $u_n(a, b, c, d) = u_n(ad, bd, cd, 1)$ for $n \geq 1$, it will often be convenient to retain the d parameter. For example, this often leads to nicer determinantal expressions for recurrent sequences as well as allowing one to see certain special cases more readily (see, e.g., the proofs of Corollaries 1 and 2 below). Further, since we also have

$$u_n(a, b, c, d) = u_n(1, b/a, c/a, ad) = \text{perm}(U_n(1, -b/a, -c/a, -ad)),$$

one can obtain formulas if desired for the recurrent sequences below as determinants or permanents, respectively, of Toeplitz–Hessenberg matrices with unit superdiagonal entries.

Define the generating function $u(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} u_n x^n$. Then $u(x)$ has the following explicit formula.

Lemma 3. *We have*

$$u(x) = \frac{dx(b + c + acdx)}{1 + d(2a - b - c)x + ad^2(a - c)x^2}. \tag{7}$$

Proof. Note first that

$$\sum_{i \geq 1} a_i x^i = \sum_{i \geq 1} (bi + c)d^i x^i = \frac{bdx}{(1 - dx)^2} + \frac{cdx}{1 - dx} = \frac{dx(b + c - cdx)}{(1 - dx)^2}.$$

By (6), we then have

$$u(x) = \frac{\frac{dx(b+c+acdx)}{(1+adx)^2}}{1 - \frac{dx(b+c+acdx)}{(1+adx)^2}} = \frac{dx(b+c+acdx)}{1 + d(2a-b-c)x + ad^2(a-c)x^2},$$

as desired. □

Using (7), we obtain the following explicit formula involving the Fibonacci and Lucas numbers.

Corollary 1. *If $n \geq 1$, then*

$$\sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) 1^{\alpha_1} 3^{\alpha_2} \cdots ((n+1)2^{n-2})^{\alpha_n} = \begin{cases} 5^{(n-1)/2} F_{n+1}, & n \text{ odd;} \\ 5^{(n-2)/2} L_{n+1}, & n \text{ even.} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Proof. Note first that (8) may be written equivalently as

$$\sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{5}}\right)^{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{3}{5}\right)^{\alpha_2} \cdots \left(\frac{(n+1)2^{n-2}}{\sqrt{5}^n}\right)^{\alpha_n} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} F_{n+1}, & n \text{ odd;} \\ \frac{1}{5} L_{n+1}, & n \text{ even,} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

since $\alpha_1 + 2\alpha_2 + \cdots + n\alpha_n = n$ for all n -tuples $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$ under consideration in the sum. By Lemma 1, the left side of (9) is given by $u_n(-1, 1/4, 1/4, 2/\sqrt{5})$ for each $n \geq 1$. Taking $a = -1$, $b = c = 1/4$, and $d = 2/\sqrt{5}$ in Lemma 3, the left side of (9) then has generating function

$$\alpha(x) := \frac{x(\sqrt{5} - x)}{5(1 - \sqrt{5}x + x^2)}.$$

Considering the odd and even parts of $\alpha(x)$, and computing $\frac{\alpha(x) \mp \alpha(-x)}{2}$, we have

$$\alpha(x) = \frac{x}{\sqrt{5}(1 - 3x^2 + x^4)} + \frac{x^2(4 - x^2)}{5(1 - 3x^2 + x^4)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \sum_{n \geq 1} F_{2n} x^{2n-1} + \frac{1}{5} \sum_{n \geq 1} L_{2n+1} x^{2n},$$

where in the second equality we have made use of the facts

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} F_{2n} x^n = \frac{x}{1 - 3x + x^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} L_{2n+1} x^n = \frac{x(4 - x)}{1 - 3x + x^2}.$$

This implies (9) and hence (8). □

We have the following comparable formulas involving the Pell and Pell–Lucas numbers.

Corollary 2. *If $n \geq 1$, then*

$$\sum_{\beta^*=n} m_{n-1}(\beta)1^{\beta_1}(2\sqrt{2})^{\beta_2} \dots ((n-1)\sqrt{2^{n-2}})^{\beta_{n-1}} = \begin{cases} \sqrt{2}P_{n-1}, & n \text{ odd}; \\ \frac{1}{2}Q_{n-1}, & n \text{ even}, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha)(\sqrt{2})^{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\alpha_2} \dots \left(\frac{n+1}{\sqrt{2^n}}\right)^{\alpha_n} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}P_{n+1}, & n \text{ odd}; \\ \frac{1}{4}Q_{n+1}, & n \text{ even}, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where the first sum is over all $(n-1)$ -tuples $\beta = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1})$ of non-negative integers such that $\beta^* = 2\beta_1 + 3\beta_2 + \dots + n\beta_{n-1} = n$.

Proof. Note first that the left side of (10) may be written as

$$\sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha)0^{\alpha_1}1^{\alpha_2}(2\sqrt{2})^{\alpha_3} \dots ((n-1)\sqrt{2^{n-2}})^{\alpha_n},$$

and hence, by (5), is given by $u_n(-1, 1/2, -1/2, \sqrt{2})$ for $n \geq 1$. By (7), we have

$$\delta(x) := \sum_{n \geq 1} u_n(-1, 1/2, -1/2, \sqrt{2})x^n = \frac{x^2}{1 - 2\sqrt{2}x + x^2}.$$

Considering the odd and even parts of $\delta(x)$ yields

$$\delta(x) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}x^3}{1 - 6x^2 + x^4} + \frac{x^2(1 + x^2)}{1 - 6x^2 + x^4} = \sqrt{2} \sum_{n \geq 1} P_{2n-2}x^{2n-1} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n \geq 1} Q_{2n-1}x^{2n},$$

which implies (10), where we have used the facts

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} P_{2n}x^n = \frac{2x}{1 - 6x + x^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{n \geq 1} Q_{2n-1}x^n = \frac{2x(1 + x)}{1 - 6x + x^2}.$$

A comparable proof may be given for (11), upon observing that the left side of (11) is given by $u_n(-1, 1, 1, 1/\sqrt{2})$ for $n \geq 1$, and hence has generating function $\frac{x(2\sqrt{2}-x)}{2(1-2\sqrt{2}x+x^2)}$. \square

Let $v_n = v_n(p, q, r, s)$ denote the Horadam sequence given by $v_n = rv_{n-1} + sv_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 2$, with $v_0 = p$ and $v_1 = q$. Then we have the following general representation of v_n .

Theorem 1. *Let p, q, r, s be complex numbers with $(q-r)^2 = 4s(p-1) \neq 0$. If $v_n = v_n(p, q, r, s)$ denotes the corresponding Horadam sequence, then*

$$v_n = \sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} \left(\frac{r-q}{2}\right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\left(q + \frac{2ps}{r-q}\right) i - \frac{2ps}{r-q} \right)^{\alpha_i}, \quad n \geq 1. \quad (12)$$

Conversely, the sequence v_n defined by (12) for all $n \geq 1$ satisfies $v_n = rv_{n-1} + sv_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 3$.

Proof. To show (12), we first seek a, b, c, d such that $v_n = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for all $n \geq 1$. In order for this to hold, we need the corresponding equality of generating functions, i.e., $v(x) = u(x)$, where

$$v(x) = \sum_{n \geq 1} v_n x^n = \frac{x(q + psx)}{1 - rx - sx^2}$$

and $u(x)$ is given by (7). This leads to the following system of equations in the unknowns a, b, c, d :

$$(i) d(b + c) = q, \quad (ii) acd^2 = ps, \quad (iii) d(b + c - 2a) = r, \quad (iv) ad^2(c - a) = s,$$

where p, q, r, s are fixed.

Subtracting equation (iii) from (i), and also (iv) from (ii), gives $2ad = q - r$ and $(ad)^2 = ps - s$. Since $(q - r)^2 = 4s(p - 1)$, by assumption, these last two equations are equivalent to one another. From $ad = \frac{q-r}{2} \neq 0$, we then get

$$cd = \frac{ps}{ad} = \frac{2ps}{q - r} \quad \text{and} \quad bd = q - cd = \frac{q^2 - rq - 2ps}{q - r}.$$

Note that once $d \neq 0$ is specified, then a, b, c are uniquely determined. That is, for $d \neq 0$, we have

$$v_n = u_n(a, b, c, d) = u_n\left(\frac{q - r}{2d}, \frac{q^2 - rq - 2ps}{d(q - r)}, \frac{2ps}{d(q - r)}, d\right), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Hence, by (5), we get

$$\begin{aligned} v_n &= \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} (-a)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n ((bi + c)d^i)^{\alpha_i} \\ &= d^n \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} \left(\frac{r - q}{2d}\right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{q^2 - rq - 2ps}{d(q - r)}i + \frac{2ps}{d(q - r)}\right)^{\alpha_i} \\ &= \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} \left(\frac{r - q}{2}\right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\left(q + \frac{2ps}{r - q}\right)i - \frac{2ps}{r - q}\right)^{\alpha_i}, \end{aligned}$$

which yields (12).

Conversely, suppose v_n for $n \geq 1$ is the sequence defined by (12), where p, q, r, s are as stated above. By (5), we have $v_n = u_n(a, b, c, d)$, where $a = \frac{q-r}{2}$, $b = q - \frac{2ps}{q-r}$, $c = \frac{2ps}{q-r}$, and $d = 1$. Applying (7) yields

$$\sum_{n \geq 1} v_n x^n = \frac{x(q + psx)}{1 - rx + \frac{q-r}{2} \left(\frac{q-r}{2} - \frac{2ps}{q-r}\right) x^2} = \frac{x(q + psx)}{1 - rx - sx^2},$$

upon making use of the assumption $(q - r)^2 = 4s(p - 1)$. The last equality above implies $v_n = rv_{n-1} + sv_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 3$, which completes the proof. \square

Taking specific cases of Theorem 1 yields determinantal representations of several second-order recurrent sequences.

Corollary 3. *If $n \geq 1$, then*

$$\sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) 3^{\alpha_1} (-4)^{\alpha_2} \dots ((-1)^{n-1} (n+2))^{\alpha_n} = F_{n+3}, \tag{13}$$

$$\sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) 2^{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{5}{4}\right)^{\alpha_2} \dots \left(\frac{n+3}{2^n}\right)^{\alpha_n} = \frac{1}{4} F_{2n+4}, \tag{14}$$

$$\sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) 6^{\alpha_1} (-10)^{\alpha_2} \dots ((-1)^{n-1} (4n+2))^{\alpha_n} = 2F_{3n+1}, \tag{15}$$

$$\sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) 5^{\alpha_1} (-14)^{\alpha_2} \dots ((-2)^{n-1} (2n+3))^{\alpha_n} = J_{n+3}, \tag{16}$$

$$\sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) 1^{\alpha_1} 4^{\alpha_2} \dots (n2^{n-1})^{\alpha_n} = J_{2n}, \tag{17}$$

$$\sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) 4^{\alpha_1} 8^{\alpha_2} \dots (4n)^{\alpha_n} = 2F_{2n}. \tag{18}$$

Proof. To show (13)–(18), we apply (12) to $v_n = v_n(p, q, r, s)$, where

$$(p, q, r, s) = (2, 3, 1, 1), (3/4, 2, 3, -1), (2, 6, 4, 1), (3, 5, 1, 2), (0, 1, 5, -4), (0, 4, 6, -1).$$

Note that $(q - r)^2 = 4s(p - 1) \neq 0$ for each quadruple (p, q, r, s) . Applying (12) in each case then yields (13)–(18), respectively. \square

Remark 2. If $(q - r)^2 \neq 4s(p - 1)$, then the proof of Theorem 1 shows that the Horadam sequence $v_n(p, q, r, s)$ does not have the representation (12) for $n \geq 1$ as the system of equations (i)–(iv) is not consistent in this case. On the other hand, if $(q - r)^2 = 4s(p - 1) = 0$ with $s \neq 0$, then one must have $ad = 0$ in the system (i)–(iv) above. But $a = 0$ is not possible since v_n satisfies a recurrence of second, but not first, order as $s \neq 0$. Also, $d \neq 0$, for otherwise $v_n = 0$ for all $n \geq 1$. Thus, v_n fails to have the form in (12) if $(q - r)^2 = 4s(p - 1) = 0$ with $s \neq 0$ (note that if $s = 0$ and $q = r$, then trivially one has $v_n = u_n(0, 0, q, 1)$ for $n \geq 1$). For additional examples of Theorem 1, note that $v_n = F_{2n}$, $2^{1-n}F_{3n-1}$, and $2^{1-n}P_{n-1}$ are Horadam sequences with $(p, q, r, s) = (0, 1, 3, -1)$, $(2, 1, 2, 1/4)$, and $(2, 0, 1, 1/4)$, respectively, where in each case, we have $(q - r)^2 = 4s(p - 1) \neq 0$. Applying (12) then yields (1)–(3) above, which were shown in [11] by a different method.

One can also express the identities in the corollaries of this section equivalently as Toeplitz–Hessenberg determinant formulas involving the Oresme numbers. For other Oresme determinant formulas, see [11].

Corollary 4. *If $n \geq 1$, then*

$$\det(-2; O_2, O_3, \dots, O_{n+1}) = \begin{cases} \frac{5^{(n-1)/2}}{2^n} F_{n+1}, & n \text{ odd;} \\ \frac{5^{(n-2)/2}}{2^n} L_{n+1}, & n \text{ even,} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

$$\det(-4; O_0, O_1, \dots, O_{n-1}) = \begin{cases} 2^{(n+1/2)} P_{n-1}, & n \text{ odd;} \\ 2^{(n-2/2)} Q_{n-1}, & n \text{ even,} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

$$\det(-1/2; O_2, O_3, \dots, O_{n+1}) = \begin{cases} 2^{-(3n+1)/2} P_{n+1}, & n \text{ odd;} \\ 2^{-(3n+4)/2} Q_{n+1}, & n \text{ even,} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

$$\det(1/4; O_3, O_4, \dots, O_{n+2}) = 2^{-3n} F_{n+3}, \quad (22)$$

$$\det(-1/8; O_4, O_5, \dots, O_{n+3}) = 2^{-(3n+2)} F_{2n+4}, \quad (23)$$

$$\det(1/4; O_3, O_5, \dots, O_{2n+1}) = 2^{-(4n-1)} F_{3n+1}, \quad (24)$$

$$\det(1/4; O_5, O_7, \dots, O_{2n+3}) = 2^{-5n} J_{n+3}, \quad (25)$$

$$\det(-2; O_1, O_2, \dots, O_n) = 2^{-n} J_{2n}, \quad (26)$$

$$\det(-1/4; O_1, O_2, \dots, O_n) = 2^{-(3n-1)} P_{2n}. \quad (27)$$

Proof. We provide proofs of (19) and (22). Similar arguments may be given for the others using (10), (11), and (14)–(18), respectively. Dividing both sides of (8) by 2^n , rearranging factors somewhat, and noting $\alpha_1 + 2\alpha_2 + \dots + n\alpha_n = n$ for all n -tuples α under consideration in the sum yields

$$\sum_{\vec{\alpha}=n} 2^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{i+1}{2^{i+1}}\right)^{\alpha_i} = \begin{cases} \frac{5^{(n-1)/2}}{2^n} F_{n+1}, & n \text{ odd;} \\ \frac{5^{(n-2)/2}}{2^n} L_{n+1}, & n \text{ even.} \end{cases}$$

The left side of the last identity is $\det(-2; O_2, \dots, O_{n+1})$, by (5), which gives (19). Dividing both sides of (13) by 2^{3n} yields

$$\sum_{\vec{\alpha}=n} \left(-\frac{1}{4}\right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{i+2}{2^{i+2}}\right)^{\alpha_i} = 2^{-3n} F_{n+3},$$

whose left side is given by $\det(1/4; O_3, \dots, O_{n+2})$, which implies (22). □

3. Further Results

We start this section with the following general representation for translates of the Gibonacci sequence.

Theorem 2. *Let G_n denote the Gibonacci sequence with $y = G_0$ and $z = G_1$, where y and z are non-negative integers, not both zero. Let $m \geq 3$ be fixed. Then we have*

for all $n \geq 1$ the identities

$$G_{n+m} = \frac{(G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D)^{n-1}}{G_{m+1}^{n-2} (G_m \pm D)^n} \times \sum_{\vec{\alpha}=n} \left(-\frac{(G_m \pm D)^2}{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D} \right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n (\pm Di + G_m)^{\alpha_i}, \tag{28}$$

where $D = \sqrt{(-1)^m(y^2 + yz - z^2)}$ and one chooses either all plus or all minus signs with regard to the D terms. Moreover, upon slightly rewriting the pair of formulas in (28), it is seen that they correspond to identities of the form $kG_{n+m} = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for all $n \geq 1$ for some constants a, b, c, d, k , and are the only two identities of this form for fixed m, y , and z .

Proof. We start by seeking constants a, b, c, d, k such that $kG_{n+m} = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for all $n \geq 1$. Note that the sequence kG_{n+m} for $n \geq 0$ is Horadam with $(p, q, r, s) = (kG_m, kG_{m+1}, 1, 1)$. By Theorem 1 (and Remark 2), in order for kG_{n+m} to have a representation in terms of $u_n(a, b, c, d)$, it is necessary and sufficient that k satisfy $(kG_{m+1} - 1)^2 = 4(kG_m - 1) \neq 0$. Note that the $\neq 0$ requirement is redundant here, and hence may be disregarded, as the equality clearly cannot hold for $k = \frac{1}{G_m}$ or $\frac{1}{G_{m+1}}$, as $m \geq 3$ and G_0, G_1 non-negative, and not both zero, implies $G_m \neq G_{m+1}$. Thus, we seek k satisfying $G_{m+1}^2 k^2 - 2(G_{m+2} + G_m)k + 5 = 0$, i.e.,

$$k = \frac{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm \sqrt{(G_{m+2} + G_m)^2 - 5G_{m+1}^2}}{G_{m+1}^2}.$$

We now show that the discriminant in the formula for k is invariant upon replacing m with $m - 2$, that is, $(G_{m+2} + G_m)^2 - 5G_{m+1}^2 = (G_m + G_{m-2})^2 - 5G_{m-1}^2$, which holds if and only if

$$(G_{m+2} + 2G_m + G_{m-2})(G_{m+2} - G_{m-2}) = 5G_m(G_{m+1} + G_{m-1}).$$

The last equality follows from comparing factors on both sides and noting the pair of relations $G_{m+2} + G_{m-2} = 3G_m$ and $G_{m+2} - G_{m-2} = G_{m+1} + G_{m-1}$. Thus, the discriminant $(G_{m+2} + G_m)^2 - 5G_{m+1}^2$ equals $(G_3 + G_1)^2 - 5G_2^2 = -4(y^2 + yz - z^2)$ if m is odd and equals $(G_2 + G_0)^2 - 5G_1^2 = 4(y^2 + yz - z^2)$ if m is even. Hence, we may write

$$k = \frac{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}{G_{m+1}^2}, \tag{29}$$

where D is as stated above.

Thus, we have $kG_{n+m} = v_n(p, q, r, s)$, with

$$(p, q, r, s) = (kG_m, kG_{m+1}, 1, 1) = \left(\frac{G_m(G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D)}{G_{m+1}^2}, \frac{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}{G_{m+1}}, 1, 1 \right),$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} q(q-r) - 2ps &= \left(\frac{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}{G_{m+1}}\right) \left(\frac{2G_m \pm 2D}{G_{m+1}}\right) - \frac{2G_m(G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D)}{G_{m+1}^2} \\ &= \frac{\pm 2D(G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D)}{G_{m+1}^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Now applying Theorem 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} kG_{n+m} &= \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} \left(\frac{r-q}{2}\right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\left(\frac{q(q-r) - 2ps}{q-r}\right) i + \frac{2ps}{q-r}\right)^{\alpha_i} \\ &= \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} \left(-\frac{G_m \pm D}{G_{m+1}}\right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}{G_{m+1}(G_m \pm D)} (\pm Di + G_m)\right)^{\alpha_i} \\ &= \left(\frac{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}{G_{m+1}(G_m \pm D)}\right)^n \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} \left(\frac{-(G_m \pm D)^2}{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}\right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n (\pm Di + G_m)^{\alpha_i}, \end{aligned}$$

which implies (28), by (29).

Further, the last equality shows $kG_{n+m} = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for all $n \geq 1$, where k is given by (29) and

$$(a, b, c, d) = \left(\frac{(G_m \pm D)^2}{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}, \pm D, G_m, \frac{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}{G_{m+1}(G_m \pm D)}\right).$$

The fact that (28) corresponds to the only two identities of the form $kG_{n+m} = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ follows from the necessity observed above that k must satisfy the stated equation in order for kG_{n+m} to be represented as $u_n(a, b, c, d)$. □

Remark 3. Equation (28) also applies for $m = 0, 1, 2$ in most cases. It applies when $m = 0$, provided only the positive choice concerning the D terms is made if $z = 0$ or $y = z \neq 0$. The final statement of Theorem 2 also holds except now there is only a single identity of the form $kG_n = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for $n \geq 1$, instead of a pair, in the cases when $z = 0$ or $y = z \neq 0$. For $m = 1$ or 2 , we have that (28) is true, provided only the positive choice for the D terms is made in the cases when $m = 1$ and $y = 0$ or $m = 2$ and $z = 0$. A remark similar to that made in the $m = 0$ case concerning the last statement in Theorem 2 applies for $m = 1$ and $m = 2$ as well. Further, it should be observed that there are infinitely many ways of producing the same sequence $u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for $n \geq 1$ given four constants a, b, c, d (for example, replacing (a, b, c, d) with $(ap, bp, cp, d/p)$ for some non-zero p). In the context of the final statement of Theorem 2, this means that for a fixed k such that $kG_{n+m} = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for all $n \geq 1$, there are infinitely many choices for the parameters a, b, c, d , though the resulting identities are equivalent and will be considered the same. Finally, we have that (28) may be slightly simplified to give

$$G_{n+m} = \frac{(-G_m \mp D)^n}{G_{m+1}^{n-2}(G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D)}$$

$$\times \sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} \left(\frac{G_{m+2} + G_m \pm 2D}{(G_m \pm D)^2} \right)^{|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n (\mp Di - G_m)^{\alpha_i},$$

and a comparable simplification of subsequent formulas in this section can be made. Note that from (28), it is apparent, by a comparison with (5), that kG_{n+m} is of the form $u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for some constants a, b, c, d, k , which may then be readily identified, if desired.

Taking $(y, z) = (0, 1)$ or $(2, 1)$ in Theorem 2 yields the following identities involving translates of the Fibonacci or Lucas sequences, where $i = \sqrt{-1}$.

Corollary 5. *Let $m \geq 0$ be fixed. Then we have for all $n \geq 1$,*

$$F_{n+m} = \frac{(L_{m+1} \pm 2\lambda)^{n-1}}{F_{m+1}^{n-2} (F_m \pm \lambda)^n} \times \sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} \left(-\frac{(F_m \pm \lambda)^2}{L_{m+1} \pm 2\lambda} \right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{j=1}^n (\pm \lambda j + F_m)^{\alpha_j}, \tag{30}$$

$$L_{n+m} = \frac{(L_{m+2} + L_m \pm 2\rho)^{n-1}}{L_{m+1}^{n-2} (L_m \pm \rho)^n} \times \sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} \left(-\frac{(L_m \pm \rho)^2}{L_{m+2} + L_m \pm 2\rho} \right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{j=1}^n (\pm \rho j + L_m)^{\alpha_j}, \tag{31}$$

where

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} i, & m \text{ even;} \\ 1, & m \text{ odd,} \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \rho = \begin{cases} \sqrt{5}, & m \text{ even;} \\ \sqrt{5}i, & m \text{ odd.} \end{cases}$$

Note that the $m = 3$ case of (30) is seen to reduce to (13), upon choosing plus for the λ terms. By contrast, the companion identity of (13) obtained by choosing minus for the λ terms in (30) when $m = 3$ is given by

$$\frac{5}{9} F_{n+3} = \left(-\frac{1}{3} \right)^n \sum_{\bar{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n (5i - 10)^{\alpha_i}, \quad n \geq 1.$$

Further, when $m = 1$ in (30), it is understood that only the positive choice of signs is to be made.

Let $v_n = v_n(p, q, r, s)$ for $n \geq 0$ be a Horadam sequence with $s \neq 0$ and p, q not both zero. Such a sequence v_n will be described as *good* if $v_n = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for all $n \geq 1$ for some constants a, b, c, d . By Theorem 1 and the subsequent remarks, a Horadam sequence v_n with $s \neq 0$ is *good* if and only if $(q - r)^2 = 4s(p - 1) \neq 0$. By Theorem 2 and the subsequent remarks, the sequence kG_{n+m} , where $m \geq 0$ is fixed and k is a constant, is good if and only if k is given by (29), where only the positive

sign is taken with respect to the D terms in certain instances when $0 \leq m \leq 2$, as discussed.

We now consider cases in which kG_{n+m} is good where k is rational. Note that by the proof of Theorem 2, k rational implies a, b, c, d are each rational in the identity $kG_{n+m} = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ for $n \geq 1$. By (29), k is rational if and only if $2D$ is, where $D = \sqrt{(-1)^m(y^2 + yz - z^2)}$. Suppose y and z are positive integers and first assume m is even. Then $2D$ is integral if and only if

$$(2y + z)^2 - 5z^2 = w^2,$$

for a non-negative integer w . Solving this *Diophantine* equation for y and z , where we may assume $(y, z) = 1$ without loss of generality, yields a solution of

$$y = \frac{5j^2 - 2j\ell + \ell^2}{4} \quad \text{and} \quad z = j\ell,$$

where j and ℓ are relatively prime odd positive integers with ℓ not divisible by 5. Then for y and z as given, the identity $kG_{n+m} = u_n(a, b, c, d)$ has each of its parameters rational, and hence all of the terms of the summation in (28) are rational.

Now assume m is odd. In this case, in order for k to be rational, the integers y and z must satisfy

$$(2y + z)^2 + w^2 = 5z^2.$$

From this, we obtain

$$y = 2j\ell - \ell^2 \quad \text{and} \quad z = j^2 + \ell^2,$$

where j and ℓ are relatively prime integers with $2j - \ell$ not divisible by 5 such that y and z are positive integers. For such y and z , the summation in (28) contains only rational terms when m is odd.

Further, one could consider the general problem of determining members of a class of Horadam sequences v_n for which kv_n is good for a fixed number k . The following result addresses this problem when $k = 1$ and v_n is a modular subsequence of the Fibonacci numbers.

Proposition 2. *Let $k_n = F_{\ell n+m}$ for $n \geq 0$, where $\ell \geq 1$ and $m \geq 0$ are fixed. Among all such sequences k_n , only $k_n = F_{n+3}$ or F_{2n} correspond to good Horadam sequences.*

Proof. Recall that $k_n = F_{\ell n+m}$ satisfies the recurrence $k_n = L_\ell k_{n-1} + (-1)^{\ell+1} k_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 2$ (see, e.g., [2]), and hence the sequence k_n is Horadam with $(p, q, r, s) = (F_m, F_{\ell+m}, L_\ell, (-1)^{\ell+1})$. By Theorem 1, we then seek all solutions to

$$(F_{\ell+m} - L_\ell)^2 = 4(-1)^{\ell+1}(F_m - 1) \neq 0, \quad \ell \geq 1, m \geq 0. \tag{32}$$

First assume $\ell = 1$. Then we need $(F_{m+1} - 1)^2 = 4(F_m - 1)$, which rearranges to

$$F_{m+1}(F_{m+1} - 2) = 4F_m - 5, \quad m \geq 0. \tag{33}$$

One may verify directly that (33) fails to hold for $m = 0, 2, 4$. If $m \geq 5$, then $F_{m+1} - 2 > 4$ and hence (33) cannot hold, as the left side is strictly greater than the right. If $m = 1$, then (33) is true, but the $\neq 0$ part of (32) fails to hold. Finally, both parts of (32) are seen to hold for $(\ell, m) = (1, 3)$, and applying Theorem 1 in this case gives (13) above for F_{n+3} .

Henceforth, assume $\ell \geq 2$. If $m = 0$, then we need $L_\ell - F_\ell = 2$, where ℓ is even, in order for (32) to hold. Then $F_{\ell-1} = 1$ implies $\ell = 2$, which is seen to give (1), as $(p, q, r, s) = (0, 1, 3, -1)$ when $(\ell, m) = (2, 0)$. If $m = 1$, then both parts of (32) fail to hold as $L_\ell = F_{\ell+1} + F_{\ell-1}$ and $\ell \geq 2$. If $m = 2$, then neither part of (32) is true if $\ell \geq 3$, with only the $\neq 0$ requirement failing to hold if $\ell = 2$. Finally, suppose $m \geq 3$. In order for the equality in (32) to have a chance of being true where $\ell \geq 2$, we must require $\ell \geq 3$ be odd due to the factor of $(-1)^{\ell+1}$. It then suffices to show

$$(F_{\ell+m} - L_\ell)^2 > 4(F_m - 1), \quad \ell, m \geq 3, \tag{34}$$

which implies that the only two good Horadam sequences out of all the sequences $F_{\ell n+m}$ are F_{n+3} and F_{2n} , by the preceding. To establish (34), note first that $F_{\ell+m+1} - L_{\ell+1} \geq F_{\ell+m} - L_\ell$ holds if and only if $F_{\ell+m-1} \geq L_{\ell-1}$, with the latter inequality being true as $F_{\ell+m-1} > F_{\ell+1} \geq F_\ell + F_{\ell-2} = L_{\ell-1}$ for $\ell, m \geq 3$. Hence, for $m \geq 3$ fixed, the difference $F_{\ell+m} - L_\ell$ considered over all $\ell \geq 3$ is minimized when $\ell = 3$. Thus, in order to establish (34), it is enough to show it when $\ell = 3$. For this, one can show $F_{m+3} - L_3 \geq 4$ and $F_{m+3} - L_3 > F_m - 1$. The last two inequalities are apparent as $m \geq 3$ implies $F_{m+3} \geq F_6 = L_3 + 4$ and $F_{m+3} - F_m = 2F_{m+1} > L_3 - 1$. This implies (34), which completes the proof. \square

We conclude this section with an extension of Theorem 2 to modular subsequences of the Gibonacci numbers.

Theorem 3. *Let G_n denote the Gibonacci sequence with $y = G_0$ and $z = G_1$, where y and z are non-negative integers, not both zero. Let $\ell \geq 1$ and $m \geq 0$ be fixed integers. If $m \geq \ell + 2$, then we have for all $n \geq 1$ the pair of identities*

$$G_{\ell n+m} = \frac{(L_\ell G_{\ell+m} - 2(-1)^\ell G_m \pm 2E)^{n-1}}{G_{\ell+m}^{n-2} ((-1)^{\ell+1} G_m \pm E)^n} \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} \left(\frac{-((-1)^{\ell+1} G_m \pm E)^2}{L_\ell G_{\ell+m} - 2(-1)^\ell G_m \pm 2E} \right)^{n-|\alpha|} \times m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n (\pm Ei - (-1)^\ell G_m)^{\alpha_i}, \tag{35}$$

where

$$E = \begin{cases} \sqrt{(-1)^\ell G_\ell (G_\ell - L_\ell y) + y^2}, & m \text{ even;} \\ \sqrt{(-1)^\ell G_{\ell+1} (G_{\ell+1} - L_\ell z) + z^2}, & m \text{ odd.} \end{cases}$$

Moreover, if $0 \leq m \leq \ell + 1$, then either of the identities in (35) holds provided there is no division by zero, and to ensure this, it suffices to verify that $G_{\ell+m}((-1)^{\ell+1}G_m \pm E)$ is not zero, given the choice of sign.

Proof. We first show (35), extending the proof given above for (28) and emphasizing the principal modifications. To do so, first note that the sequence $kG_{\ell n+m}$ for $n \geq 0$, where k is a constant, is Horadam with $(p, q, r, s) = (kG_m, kG_{\ell+m}, L_\ell, (-1)^{\ell+1})$. We then seek k such that

$$(kG_{\ell+m} - L_\ell)^2 = 4(-1)^{\ell+1}(kG_m - 1) \neq 0,$$

i.e.,

$$k = \frac{L_\ell G_{\ell+m} + 2(-1)^{\ell+1}G_m \pm \sqrt{(L_\ell G_{\ell+m} + 2(-1)^{\ell+1}G_m)^2 - 5F_\ell^2 G_{\ell+m}^2}}{G_{\ell+m}^2},$$

where we have used the fact $L_\ell^2 + 4(-1)^{\ell+1} = 5F_\ell^2$ for $\ell \geq 1$ in simplifying the discriminant. Let us assume for now that $k \neq L_\ell/G_{\ell+m}$ so that the not equal zero part of the criterion concerning k from Theorem 1 is satisfied.

To simplify k , we first demonstrate the invariance of the discriminant of k when m is replaced by $m - 2$ for each $m \geq 2$. Proceeding as before, we need to verify the identity

$$\begin{aligned} & (L_\ell(G_{\ell+m} + G_{\ell+m-2}) + 2(-1)^{\ell+1}(G_m + G_{m-2}))(L_\ell G_{\ell+m-1} + 2(-1)^{\ell+1}G_{m-1}) \\ & = 5F_\ell^2 G_{\ell+m-1}(G_{\ell+m} + G_{\ell+m-2}). \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

To establish (36), it suffices to show the following pair of identities for all $\ell \geq 1$, $m \geq 2$:

$$L_\ell(G_{\ell+m} + G_{\ell+m-2}) + 2(-1)^{\ell+1}(G_m + G_{m-2}) = 5F_\ell G_{\ell+m-1}, \tag{37}$$

$$L_\ell G_{\ell+m-1} + 2(-1)^{\ell+1}G_{m-1} = F_\ell(G_{\ell+m} + G_{\ell+m-2}). \tag{38}$$

For (37) and (38), it is enough to prove them when $(y, z) = (0, 1)$, i.e., when G_a is replaced by F_a in all of the G_a terms, since G_a is a linear combination of the F_a (recall $G_a = yF_{a-1} + zF_a$ for all a). That (37) and (38) hold for all ℓ and m when $G_a = F_a$ is most readily shown by making use of the Binet formulas for F_a and L_a .

By the invariance established above, we then have

$$(L_\ell G_{\ell+m} - 2(-1)^\ell G_m)^2 - 5F_\ell^2 G_{\ell+m}^2 = \begin{cases} (L_\ell G_\ell - 2(-1)^\ell y)^2 - 5F_\ell^2 G_\ell^2, & m \text{ even;} \\ (L_\ell G_{\ell+1} - 2(-1)^\ell z)^2 - 5F_\ell^2 G_{\ell+1}^2, & m \text{ odd.} \end{cases}$$

The latter expression is seen to coincide with $4E^2$, where E is as stated above, upon expanding and using the fact $L_\ell^2 - 5F_\ell^2 = 4(-1)^\ell$, whence

$$k = \frac{L_\ell G_{\ell+m} + 2(-1)^{\ell+1}G_m \pm 2E}{G_{\ell+m}^2}. \tag{39}$$

Thus, we have that $kG_{\ell n+m}$ is a good Horadam sequence if and only if k is given by (39), in which case $kG_{\ell n+m} = v_n(p, q, r, s)$, with

$$(p, q, r, s) = \left(\frac{G_m(L_\ell G_{\ell+m} - 2(-1)^\ell G_m \pm 2E)}{G_{\ell+m}^2}, \frac{L_\ell G_{\ell+m} - 2(-1)^\ell G_m \pm 2E}{G_{\ell+m}}, L_\ell, (-1)^{\ell+1} \right).$$

Substituting now into (12), and proceeding as before in the simplification, yields (35).

We now show that if $m \geq \ell + 2$, then both choices of sign yield a valid identity in (35). First of all, we must have $G_{\ell+m} \neq 0$; otherwise, one could not apply the quadratic formula in ascertaining k and the expressions in (35) and (39) would contain a discontinuity. In order for $G_{\ell+m}$ to be zero, where y, z are non-negative and not both zero, with $\ell \geq 1$ and $m \geq 0$, we must have $\ell = 1, m = 0$, and $z = 0$. Note that this case would technically not apply for $m \geq \ell + 2$, i.e., the factor $G_{\ell+m}$ would always be nonzero for such ℓ and m .

From Theorem 1, in order to apply (12) to $kG_{\ell n+m}$ in deriving (35), we have that the common value of both sides of the equality must be nonzero in the necessary (and sufficient) condition for k given by $(kG_{\ell+m} - L_\ell)^2 = 4(-1)^{\ell+1}(kG_m - 1)$. Thus, in order to demonstrate that both choices of sign yield a valid identity in (35) when $m \geq \ell + 2$, it suffices to show that for both of the possibilities for k in (39), we have $k \neq L_\ell/G_{\ell+m}$. Note that $k = L_\ell/G_{\ell+m}$ if and only if $(-1)^{\ell+1}G_m \pm E = 0$, which is seen to introduce division by zero in (35). So it is enough to show that the equality

$$(-1)^{\ell+1}G_m = \pm E \tag{40}$$

cannot hold if $m \geq \ell + 2$.

To do so, first note that if the radicand in E is negative, then (40) clearly cannot hold, so we assume that the radicand is non-negative. Thus, it is enough to show

$$G_m^2 > E^2, \tag{41}$$

for $m \geq \ell + 2$ when E is a (non-negative) real number. We consider cases on the parity of ℓ , first assuming ℓ is odd. If m is odd, by the stated formula for E , we have that (41) holds if and only if $G_m^2 - z^2 > G_{\ell+1}(zL_\ell - G_{\ell+1})$. Since y and z are non-negative, it follows that G_m is increasing in m for fixed values of y and z . Therefore, to demonstrate the last inequality for all odd $m \geq \ell + 2$, we only need to consider the case where $m = \ell + 2$.

Then we must establish

$$(G_{\ell+2} + z)(G_{\ell+2} - z) > G_{\ell+1}(zL_\ell - G_{\ell+1}). \tag{42}$$

Note (42) clearly holds if $z = 0$ since $y > 0$ in this case, and hence we may assume $z > 0$. Further, we have

$$zL_\ell - G_{\ell+1} = z(F_{\ell+1} + F_{\ell-1}) - (yF_\ell + zF_{\ell+1}) = zF_{\ell-1} - yF_\ell, \quad \ell \geq 1.$$

Then $z > 0$ implies $G_{\ell+2} + z > G_{\ell+1} > 0$ and

$$G_{\ell+2} - z = yF_{\ell+1} + z(F_{\ell+2} - 1) > |zF_{\ell-1} - yF_{\ell}|, \quad \ell \geq 1.$$

Thus, upon comparing the respective left and right factors of the two sides, one obtains (42). If m is even, then (41) is equivalent to $G_m^2 - y^2 > G_{\ell}(yL_{\ell} - G_{\ell})$. Then $m \geq \ell + 2$ and m even implies in fact $m \geq \ell + 3$, and it is enough to show the last inequality when $m = \ell + 3$, which can be done in a similar manner as before. A comparable proof, which we omit, based on cases with regard to the parity of m may be given for (41) when ℓ is even, which completes the proof of (41). Thus, we have that (40) cannot hold for all $\ell \geq 1$ and $m \geq \ell + 2$, as desired.

Further, if $\ell \geq 2$, then one can show that $L_{\ell}G_{\ell+m} + 2(-1)^{\ell+1}G_m \pm 2E > 0$ in all cases when E is real, and hence this factor is always nonzero in (35) for such ℓ . If $\ell = 1$, then this factor is zero only when $m = z = 0$ and minus is chosen, but this case is already covered by the prior considerations given for the $G_{\ell+m}$ factor. Thus, division by zero in (35) can only occur when $0 \leq m \leq \ell + 1$ in certain cases where y and z are such that $G_{\ell+m}((-1)^{\ell+1}G_m \pm E)$ is zero. This implies the final statement in Theorem 3 and completes the proof. \square

The second statement in Theorem 3 is also seen to apply to the identities in (35) for fixed ℓ and m , where there is only a single identity of the stated form in cases where a choice of one of the signs leads to division by zero. Taking $\ell = 1$ in (35) is seen to yield (28). Taking $\ell = 2$ in (35) gives the following explicit formulas for the Gibonacci half-sequences G_{2n+m} for a fixed m .

Corollary 6. *For each $m \geq 4$ fixed, there is the following pair of identities for all $n \geq 1$:*

$$G_{2n+m} = \frac{(G_{m+3} + G_{m+1} \pm 2F)^{n-1}}{G_{m+2}^{n-2}(-G_m \pm F)^n} \times \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} \left(-\frac{(-G_m \pm F)^2}{G_{m+3} + G_{m+1} \pm 2F} \right)^{n-|\alpha|} m_n(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n (\pm Fi - G_m)^{\alpha_i}, \tag{43}$$

where $F = \sqrt{(-1)^{m+1}(y^2 + yz - z^2)}$ with $y = G_0, z = G_1$. Further, if $0 \leq m \leq 3$, then both identities in (43) hold except in the following cases where only the negative choice of sign leads to a valid expression: (i) $m = 0$ and $2y = z$, (ii) $m = 1$ and $y = z$, (iii) $m = 2$ and $y = 0$, or (iv) $m = 3$ and $z = 0$.

Taking $(y, z) = (0, 1)$ or $(2, 1)$ in (43) gives analogues of the formulas from Corollary 5 for the Fibonacci and Lucas half-sequences.

4. Combinatorial Proofs

In this section, we provide combinatorial arguments for most of the formulas from Corollaries 2 and 3 above as well as for the prior identity (3), which was shown in [11] by an algebraic argument. To do so, we will enumerate several structures involving $(m + r)$ -color compositions of n . Recall that a *composition* of a positive integer n is a sequence of positive integers, called *parts*, whose sum is n . Given a non-negative integer r , an $(m + r)$ -color composition of n is one in which a part of size a for each $a \geq 1$ is assigned one of $a + r$ colors. This color is often denoted by a subscript on the part in question. Thus, an $(m + r)$ -color composition π may be represented as $\pi = ((a_1)_{b_1}, \dots, (a_k)_{b_k})$ for some $k \geq 1$, where $a_i \geq 1$ for $1 \leq i \leq k$ with $\sum_{i=1}^k a_i = n$ and $b_i \in [a_i + r]$ for each i . The notion of an m -color composition was introduced in [1] and has been an ongoing object of study. See [5], where $(am + b)$ -color compositions were studied for fixed a and b . Let \mathcal{C}_n denote the set of m -color compositions of n . A fundamental result (see, e.g., [1]) states that the cardinality of \mathcal{C}_n is given by F_{2n} for all $n \geq 1$.

We will also make use of linear tiling structures in several of our proofs below. By a *tile*, we mean a $1 \times m$ rectangular piece for some $m \geq 1$ capable of covering m consecutive positions. *Squares* and *dominos* correspond to 1×1 and 1×2 tiles, which will be denoted by s and d , respectively. A covering of the numbers $1, 2, \dots, n$, written in a row, by non-overlapping squares and dominos is referred to as a *square-and-domino tiling* of length n , the set of which will be denoted here by \mathcal{F}_n . Recall that $|\mathcal{F}_n| = F_{n+1}$ for all $n \geq 0$; see, e.g., [4, Chapter 1]. Note that members of \mathcal{F}_n may be viewed as sequences of $n - 2m$ squares and m dominos for some $0 \leq m \leq \lfloor n/2 \rfloor$, or equivalently as compositions of n whose parts belong to $\{1, 2\}$.

We start with a combinatorial argument for the first identity in Corollary 2.

Proof of (10). We first consider the even case of (10), which may be written equivalently as

$$Q_{n-1} = \sum_{\beta^*=n} 2^{\frac{n+2}{2}-|\beta|} m_{n-1}(\beta) 1^{\beta_1} 2^{\beta_2} \dots (n-1)^{\beta_{n-1}}, \quad n \geq 2 \text{ even}, \quad (44)$$

where the sum is over all $\beta = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1})$ such that $\beta^* = 2\beta_1 + \dots + n\beta_{n-1} = n$. One may verify (44) in the cases when $n = 2$ or 4 , so assume $n \geq 6$. Let d_k denote the right-hand side of (44) where $n = 2k$ for $k \geq 1$. To establish (44), it suffices to show $d_k = 6d_{k-1} - d_{k-2}$ for $k \geq 3$, as the two sides agree when $k = 1, 2$. Let \mathcal{C}'_n denote the set of m -color compositions of n in which no parts with subscript one are allowed. Given $\lambda \in \mathcal{C}'_n$, suppose that the vector recording the multiplicities of the part sizes of λ is given by β for some β such that $\beta^* = n$. That is, for each $i \in [n - 1]$, there are exactly β_i parts of size $i + 1$ in the composition λ . For each λ , define S_λ to be the set of binary words of length $\frac{n+2}{2} - \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \beta_i$. Let \mathcal{D}_k denote

the set of all ordered pairs (λ, ω) , where $\lambda \in \mathcal{C}'_{2k}$ and $\omega \in S_\lambda$. Then it is seen that $d_k = |\mathcal{D}_k|$ for all $k \geq 1$. Using this combinatorial interpretation for d_k , we will establish the recurrence stated above for d_k .

To do so, first consider appending the (colored) part 2_2 to λ' in $x' = (\lambda', \omega') \in \mathcal{D}_{k-1}$ to obtain $x = (\lambda, \omega) \in \mathcal{D}_k$ wherein λ ends in 2_2 . Note that we take $\omega = \omega'$ since the difference $k - \sum_{i \geq 1} \beta_i$ is maintained in going from λ' to λ , as both k and $\sum_{i \geq 1} \beta_i$ are increased by one in this case. This yields d_{k-1} possibilities for such x . Now consider adding two to the final part of λ' , but not its subscript, and then appending 0 or 1 to ω' to obtain x from x' . Note that adding 0 or 1 to ω' is required in this case since the difference $k - \sum_{i \geq 1} \beta_i$ with regard to x' is increased by one by such an operation on λ' , as k increases by one (i.e., n increases by two), but the number of parts remains the same. This then yields $2d_{k-1}$ members $x \in \mathcal{D}_k$ wherein the final part of λ exceeds its subscript by at least two.

Now suppose λ within $x = (\lambda, \omega) \in \mathcal{D}_k$ has final part a_b , where $a \geq 3$ and $b = a$ or $a - 1$. We must show that such members x within \mathcal{D}_k number $3d_{k-1} - d_{k-2}$. To do so, first let J and L denote two copies of the set \mathcal{D}_{k-1} . Let $x' = (\lambda', \omega') \in J$. If the final part of λ' is at least 3, and not a_a for some a , then reduce the final part, but not its subscript, by one and append 3_2 to λ' . On the other hand, if the final part is a_a for some $a \geq 2$, then replace the final part of λ' with $(a + 2)_{a+2}$. In the latter case, we also add 0 to the end of ω' to obtain x from x' . If $x' \in K$, then we perform comparable operations as before, but append 3_3 to λ' , instead of 3_2 , if the final part of λ' is not a_a , and add 1 to the end of ω' , instead of 0, in cases when it is.

Let S denote the subset of \mathcal{D}_k consisting of those (λ, ω) wherein the final part a_b satisfies $a \geq 4$ with $b = a - 1$. At this point, all the members of $\mathcal{D}_k - S$ have been enumerated, and are seen to have cardinality $5d_{k-1}$, so to complete the proof of the recurrence for d_k , we must show $|S| = d_{k-1} - d_{k-2}$. To do so, first note that there are $d_{k-1} - 2d_{k-2}$ members $(\lambda', \omega') \in \mathcal{D}_{k-1}$ in which the final part of λ' is c_d , where $c = d = 2$ or $c \geq 3$ with $d = c$ or $c - 1$, by subtraction. To see this, take any $(\rho, \alpha) \in \mathcal{D}_{k-2}$, increase the final part of ρ by two, leaving its subscript unchanged, and then append 0 or 1 to α to obtain the excluded members of \mathcal{D}_{k-1} accounted for by the subtracted term. To each $(\lambda', \omega') \in \mathcal{D}_{k-1}$ as described, we replace the final part c_d of λ' with $(c + 2)_{c+1}$ and either append 1 to ω' if $c \geq 3$ with $d = c - 1$ or append 0 to ω' if $c = d \geq 2$. Note that this yields uniquely all members of $S - S'$, where S' consists of those $(\lambda, \omega) \in S$ such that λ has final part 4_3 and ω ends in 1, and hence $|S - S'| = d_{k-1} - 2d_{k-2}$. Further, $|S'| = d_{k-2}$, upon considering an arbitrary $(\rho, \alpha) \in \mathcal{D}_{k-2}$ and appending 4_3 to ρ and 1 to α . This implies $|S| = d_{k-1} - d_{k-2}$, and hence $u_k = 6u_{k-1} - u_{k-2}$ for $k \geq 3$, as desired, which completes the proof of (44). A similar proof may be given for the odd case

of (10), rewritten as

$$P_{n-1} = \sum_{\beta^*=n} 2^{\frac{n-1}{2}-|\beta|} m_{n-1}(\beta) 1^{\beta_1} 2^{\beta_2} \dots (n-1)^{\beta_{n-1}}, \quad n \geq 1 \text{ odd},$$

where β is as before. □

Proof of (11). We first prove the odd case of (11), written equivalently as

$$2^{(n-1)/2} P_{n+1} = \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha) 2^{\alpha_1} 3^{\alpha_2} \dots (n+1)^{\alpha_n}, \quad n \geq 1 \text{ odd}, \quad (45)$$

where the sum is over all $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$ such that $\tilde{\alpha} = \alpha_1 + 2\alpha_2 + \dots + n\alpha_n = n$. One may verify (45) when $n = 1$ or 3 , so assume $n \geq 5$. Note that $b_n = P_{2n}$ implies $b_n = 6b_{n-1} - b_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 3$, and hence $2^{n-1}b_n = 12(2^{n-2}b_{n-1}) - 4(2^{n-3}b_{n-2})$. We denote the right-hand side of (45) by e_k where $n = 2k - 1$ for $k \geq 1$. To establish (45), it thus suffices to show $e_k = 12e_{k-1} - 4e_{k-2}$ for $k \geq 3$. Let \mathcal{E}_n denote the set of $(m+1)$ -color compositions of n . Then it is seen that the right side of (45) equals $|\mathcal{E}_n|$. Using the combinatorial interpretation $e_k = |\mathcal{E}_{2k-1}|$ for $k \geq 1$, we will show that e_k satisfies the recurrence stated above.

First, note that there are clearly $4e_{k-1}$ members of \mathcal{E}_n whose last two parts are $1_a, 1_{a'}$, where $a, a' \in \{1, 2\}$, and also $3e_{k-1}$ members ending in 2_b , where $b \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Further, upon increasing the final part of an arbitrary member of \mathcal{E}_{n-2} by one, but not its subscript, and subsequently appending 1_a , we have that there are $2e_{k-1}$ members of \mathcal{E}_n whose last two parts are $(c+1)_d, 1_a$, where $c \geq 1$ and $d \in [c+1]$. Note that this misses compositions with endings of the form $(c+1)_{c+2}, 1_a$, which will be accounted for below. Finally, upon increasing the last part of a member of \mathcal{E}_{n-2} by two, and leaving the subscript unchanged, we have that there are e_{k-1} members of \mathcal{E}_n whose last part is of the form $(x+2)_y$, where $x \geq 1$ and $y \in [x+1]$.

At this point, we have found $|\mathcal{E}_n - T| = 10e_{k-1}$, where T is the subset of \mathcal{E}_n whose members have final part z_z or z_{z+1} for some $z \geq 3$ or whose final two parts are $(c+1)_{c+2}, 1_a$, where $c \geq 1$. Thus, to complete the proof of the recurrence for e_k , we must show $|T| = 2e_{k-1} - 4e_{k-2}$ for $k \geq 3$. To do so, let R denote the subset of \mathcal{E}_{n-2} whose members have final part x_x or x_{x+1} for some $x \geq 1$. Note that $|R| = e_{k-1} - 2e_{k-2}$, by subtraction, upon excluding members of \mathcal{E}_{n-2} ending in 2_1 or $(x+2)_y$, where $y \in [x+1]$.

We thus need to show $|T| = 2|R|$. To do so, let J and K denote two copies of the set R . Let δ denote the final part of a member of J or K . In members of J , we increase both δ and its subscript by two to obtain all members of T ending in z_z or z_{z+1} for some $z \geq 3$. In members of K , if $\delta = x_x$, then we replace δ with the two parts $(x+1)_{x+2}, 1_1$, whereas if $\delta = x_{x+1}$, then we replace δ with $(x+1)_{x+2}, 1_2$. One then obtains the remaining members of T in this way, which establishes the desired formula for $|T|$. This completes the proof of the recurrence for e_k , and hence of

(45) as well. Rewriting the even case of (11) as

$$2^{(n-4)/2}Q_{n+1} = \sum_{\tilde{\alpha}=n} m_n(\alpha)2^{\alpha_1}3^{\alpha_2} \cdots (n+1)^{\alpha_n}, \quad n \geq 2 \text{ even,}$$

and proceeding as before, we complete the proof of (11). □

Proof of (13). Let \mathcal{G}_n denote the set of $(m+2)$ -color compositions of n . Let $\mu(\lambda)$ denote the number of parts of $\lambda \in \mathcal{G}_n$ and define the sign of λ as $(-1)^{n-\mu(\lambda)}$. Then it is seen that (13) may be written equivalently as

$$F_{n+3} = \sum_{\lambda \in \mathcal{G}_n} (-1)^{n-\mu(\lambda)}, \quad n \geq 1. \tag{46}$$

To show (46), we define a sign-changing involution on \mathcal{G}_n whose set of survivors has sum of signs given by F_{n+3} . In order to do so, let $\pi \in \mathcal{G}_n$ be represented sequentially and consider occurrences of one of the following four types involving a part or pair of parts of the stated form, where $a \geq 2$ and $c \geq 1$:

- (i) a_b , with $b \in [a+1]$,
- (ii) $c_d, 1_1$, with $d \in [c+2]$,
- (iii) a_{a+2} , or
- (iv) $c_{c+2}, 1_3$.

First, suppose π contains (i) or (ii) and consider the rightmost occurrence of (i) or (ii) within π . If this rightmost occurrence is a case of (i), then replace the part a_b , where $a \geq 2$ and $b \in [a+1]$, with the two parts $(a-1)_b, 1_1$, and vice versa if (ii), merging the two parts in question into a single part of the form (i). Note that both operations just described reverse the sign since the number of parts of a member of \mathcal{G}_n changes by one in each case. Now suppose π fails to contain (i) or (ii), but contains at least one occurrence of (iii) or (iv). If the rightmost occurrence of either (iii) or (iv) corresponds to a case of (iii), then replace a_{a+2} where $a \geq 2$ with $(a-1)_{a+1}, 1_3$, and vice versa, merging the two parts in question, if the occurrence corresponds to (iv). Again, these operations reverse the sign for all π for which they are defined. Combining the two preceding pairs of operations then defines a sign-reversing involution θ on all members of \mathcal{G}_n which witness at least one of (i)–(iv). In particular, note that applying the second pair of operations to members of \mathcal{G}_n which are free of (i) and (ii) does not introduce an occurrence of (i) or (ii).

Let \mathcal{G}'_n denote the subset of \mathcal{G}_n for which θ is not defined. One may verify that members of \mathcal{G}'_n consist exclusively of parts of size 1 subject to the following restrictions:

- (i) the part 1_1 can only occur at the very beginning, if at all, and
- (ii) each part 1_3 must be preceded by 1_1 or 1_2 , or occur at the very beginning.

Note that each member of \mathcal{G}'_n has positive sign, consisting only of parts of size one, and thus we seek $|\mathcal{G}'_n|$. To determine $|\mathcal{G}'_n|$, first suppose $\rho \in \mathcal{G}'_n$ does not start

with 1_1 . Then ρ is a sequence of length n consisting of the parts 1_2 and 1_3 such that no two parts 1_3 are adjacent. Such sequences are seen to be in one-to-one correspondence with subsets of $[n]$ containing no two adjacent elements. It follows then from [17, p.46, Exercise 14a] that there are F_{n+2} members of \mathcal{G}'_n not starting with 1_1 . On the other hand, if ρ does start with 1_1 , then we have that there are F_{n+1} possibilities, by the same reasoning. Combining the two preceding cases on ρ implies

$$|\mathcal{G}'_n| = F_{n+2} + F_{n+1} = F_{n+3},$$

which establishes (46) and completes the proof. □

Proof of (14). Note first that (14) may be written in the more suggestive form

$$2^{n-2}F_{2n+4} = |\mathcal{H}_n|, \quad n \geq 1, \tag{47}$$

where \mathcal{H}_n denotes the set of $(m+3)$ -color compositions of n . Equation (47) holds for $n = 1$ or 2 , as there are 4 and 21 members of \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 , respectively, and hence we may assume $n \geq 3$. Recall that the sequence $b_n = F_{2n+4}$ satisfies the recurrence $b_n = 3b_{n-1} - b_{n-2}$, and hence $c_n = 2^{n-2}b_n$ satisfies $c_n = 6c_{n-1} - 4c_{n-2}$. Let $h_n = |\mathcal{H}_n|$ for $n \geq 1$. To establish (47), it thus suffices to show $h_n = 6h_{n-1} - 4h_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 3$. To do so, first note that there are clearly $4h_{n-1}$ members of \mathcal{H}_n whose last part is 1_b for some $b \in [4]$. Further, there are h_{n-1} members of \mathcal{H}_n whose last part is $(a+1)_b$ for some $a \geq 1$ and $b \in [a+3]$, upon adding one to the final part of an arbitrary member of \mathcal{H}_{n-1} , but not its subscript.

It remains to enumerate the subset S of \mathcal{H}_n consisting of those compositions having last part a_{a+3} for some $a \geq 2$. To do so, consider the subset \mathcal{H}'_n of \mathcal{H}_n consisting of those compositions that do not have last part $1_1, 1_2, 1_3$, or c_d for some $c \geq 2$ and $d \in [c+2]$. Note that adding one to both the last part of a member of \mathcal{H}'_{n-1} and its subscript defines a bijection between \mathcal{H}'_{n-1} and S . Thus, we have

$$|S| = |\mathcal{H}'_{n-1}| = h_{n-1} - 4h_{n-2}, \quad n \geq 3,$$

where the second equality follows from a straightforward subtraction argument. Combining this case with the prior ones yields the desired recurrence for h_n , which establishes (47) and completes the proof. □

Proof of (17). Let \mathcal{J}_n denote the set of $m2^{m-1}$ -color compositions of n . We represent a part of size a within a member of \mathcal{J}_n as a_b , where $a \geq 1, b \in [a]$, and members of $[2, a]$ may be marked. Note that a separate independent marking of the members of $[2, a]$ is to be made for each part of size a for all a (which may be viewed as a tile composed of a unit squares, all but the first of which may be marked). Then the left-hand side of (17) is seen to give $|\mathcal{J}_n|$, and we seek to show $|\mathcal{J}_n| = J_{2n}$ for all $n \geq 1$. By a *Jacobsthal* tiling, we mean a square-and-domino tiling in which dominos may be marked. Using its recurrence and initial values, one

can show that J_n for $n \geq 1$ enumerates the Jacobsthal tilings of length $n - 1$. Let \mathcal{L}_n denote the set of Jacobsthal tilings of length $2n - 1$. To show $|\mathcal{J}_n| = J_{2n}$, it then suffices to define a bijection between \mathcal{J}_n and \mathcal{L}_n . In order to do so, we consider an intermediate structure \mathcal{K}_n consisting of all 5-ary words of length $n - 1$ in which neither a 4 nor 5 can follow a 2 or 3.

Below, we construct bijections (i) $f : \mathcal{K}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{J}_n$ and (ii) $g : \mathcal{K}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{L}_n$, whence the desired bijection between \mathcal{J}_n and \mathcal{L}_n is obtained by taking $g \circ f^{-1}$.

(i) *Bijection between \mathcal{K}_n and \mathcal{J}_n .* To define f , let $\pi \in \mathcal{K}_n$, where we henceforth may assume $n \geq 2$. We decompose π as $\pi = \pi^{(0)}\pi^{(1)} \dots \pi^{(r)}$ for some $r \geq 0$, where the section $\pi^{(i)}$ for each $i \in [r]$ is nonempty, starts with 1, and contains no other 1's, with $\pi^{(0)}$ possibly empty and containing no 1's. We further decompose each $\pi^{(i)}$ for $i \in [r]$ as $\pi^{(i)} = 1\alpha^{(i)}\beta^{(i)}$, where $\alpha^{(i)}$ and $\beta^{(i)}$ if nonempty contain only letters in $\{4, 5\}$ and $\{2, 3\}$, respectively, and likewise decompose $\pi^{(0)}$ as $\pi^{(0)} = \alpha^{(0)}\beta^{(0)}$. Note that these decompositions for the $\pi^{(i)}$ follow from the requirement that no 4 or 5 can follow a 2 or 3 within π .

Using this decomposition for π , one can create a member of \mathcal{J}_n as follows. Let $a_i = |\alpha^{(i)}|$ and $b_i = |\beta^{(i)}|$ for each i . Define

$$f(\pi) = ((a_0 + b_0 + 1)_{a_0+1}, (a_1 + b_1 + 1)_{a_1+1}, \dots, (a_r + b_r + 1)_{a_r+1}),$$

wherein for each $0 \leq i \leq r$, the p -th member, where $1 \leq p \leq a_i$, of $[2, a_i + 1]$ is marked if and only if the p -th letter of the section $\alpha^{(i)}$ is a 4, and likewise the p -th member, where $1 \leq p \leq b_i$, of $[a_i + 2, a_i + b_i + 1]$ is marked if and only if the p -th letter of $\beta^{(i)}$ is a 2. One may verify that $f(\pi) \in \mathcal{J}_n$ for all $\pi \in \mathcal{K}_n$ such that the number of parts in $f(\pi)$ is one more than the number of 1's in π . The mapping f is seen to be reversible, and constructing its inverse is straightforward. Hence, f provides the desired bijection between \mathcal{K}_n and \mathcal{J}_n .

(ii) *Bijection between \mathcal{K}_n and \mathcal{L}_n .* To define the mapping g , we represent $\pi \in \mathcal{K}_n$ as $\pi = \pi^{(0)}\pi^{(1)} \dots \pi^{(r)}$ like before. Let

$$g(\pi) = d^{a_0}sd^{b_0}(sd^{a_1}sd^{b_1}) \dots (sd^{a_r}sd^{b_r}),$$

where d^j denotes a run of dominos of length $j \geq 0$ and the p -th domino in the run d^{a_i} or d^{b_i} for each $0 \leq i \leq r$ is marked if and only if the p -th letter of $\alpha^{(i)}$ or $\beta^{(i)}$ is 4 or 2, respectively. One may verify that $g(\pi)$ has length $2(n - 1) + 1 = 2n - 1$, and hence belongs to \mathcal{L}_n for each π . Further, note that π containing r letters 1 for some $r \geq 0$ implies $g(\pi)$ contains $2r + 1$ squares. To reverse g , consider decomposing an arbitrary member of \mathcal{L}_n according to its runs of dominos and noting which, if any, dominos within a particular run are marked. The mapping g then provides the desired bijection between \mathcal{K}_n and \mathcal{L}_n , which completes the proof. \square

Proof of (18). Let \mathcal{Q}_n denote the set of m -color compositions of n wherein each part of a composition is marked in one of four ways (indicated by an element of

[4]). Then the left-hand side of (18) is seen to give $|\mathcal{Q}_n|$, and we seek to show $|\mathcal{Q}_n| = 2P_{2n}$ for $n \geq 1$. It is well-known (see, e.g., [3]) that P_n for $n \geq 1$ enumerates the set of Pell tilings of length $n - 1$, which are square-and-domino tilings where squares come in one of two colors. Let \mathcal{T}_n denote the set of Pell tilings of length $2n$ ending in a square. Then $|\mathcal{T}_n| = 2P_{2n}$, and thus to establish (18), it suffices to define a bijection between \mathcal{Q}_n and \mathcal{T}_n for $n \geq 1$. To aid in doing so, we consider an intermediate structure \mathcal{R}_n consisting of 6-ary words of length n starting with a letter in [4] such that no 6 can follow a 5.

Below, we define bijections (i) $f : \mathcal{R}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{Q}_n$ and (ii) $g : \mathcal{R}_n \rightarrow \mathcal{T}_n$, whence the desired bijection between \mathcal{Q}_n and \mathcal{T}_n is obtained by taking $g \circ f^{-1}$.

(i) *Bijection between \mathcal{R}_n and \mathcal{Q}_n .* To define f , we decompose $\pi \in \mathcal{R}_n$ as

$$\pi = y_1\pi^{(1)} \cdots y_s\pi^{(s)}, \quad s \geq 1, \tag{48}$$

where $y_i \in [4]$ and $\pi^{(i)} = 6^{p_i}5^{q_i}$ for each $i \in [s]$, with $p_i, q_i \geq 0$ for all i . Note that the requirements that π starts with a letter in [4] and that no 6 follows a 5 in π allow us to decompose π as in (48). Let $f(\pi)$ be the member of \mathcal{Q}_n whose i -th part for each $i \in [s]$ is given by $(p_i + q_i + 1)_{p_i+1}$, with this part being marked according to $y_i \in [4]$. Then f can be reversed upon considering the number of parts in an arbitrary member of \mathcal{Q}_n as well as how each part is marked. Thus, the mapping f provides the desired bijection between \mathcal{R}_n and \mathcal{Q}_n .

(ii) *Bijection between \mathcal{R}_n and \mathcal{T}_n .* Let $\rho \in \mathcal{R}_n$, where we may assume $n \geq 2$. In order to define g , we decompose ρ as

$$\rho = x_0\rho^{(0)}x_1\rho^{(1)} \cdots x_r\rho^{(r)}$$

for some $r \geq 0$, where $x_i \in [4]$ for each $0 \leq i \leq r$ and the section $\rho^{(i)}$ for $i \in [r]$ is given by

$$\rho^{(i)} = 6^{j_i}a_1^{(i)}a_2^{(i)} \cdots a_{k_i}^{(i)}, \quad j_i \geq 1, k_i \geq 0, \tag{49}$$

with the letters $a_1^{(i)}, a_2^{(i)}, \dots, a_{k_i}^{(i)}$ each belonging to [5]. The section $\rho^{(0)}$ is of the same form except that $j_0 = 0$ is also allowed. One may verify that ρ may be decomposed as described above since it must start with a letter in [4], with no 6 following a 5.

Let us represent the two kinds of colored squares in a Pell tiling by b and w standing for black and white, respectively. Define the function $\delta : [5] \rightarrow \mathcal{P}_2$ by $\delta(1) = b^2$, $\delta(2) = bw$, $\delta(3) = wb$, $\delta(4) = w^2$, and $\delta(5) = d$. Consider replacing each section $x_i\rho^{(i)}$ of ρ , where $\rho^{(i)}$ is given by (49), with the tiling T_i defined by

$$T_i = d^{j_i} _ \delta(a_1^{(i)})\delta(a_2^{(i)}) \cdots \delta(a_{k_i}^{(i)}) _, \quad 0 \leq i \leq r,$$

where the two blank positions are to be filled by the first and second squares, respectively, of $\delta(x_i)$. Let $g(\rho) = T_0T_1 \cdots T_r$, where it is understood that the tilings T_i are concatenated.

One may verify $g(\rho) \in \mathcal{Q}_n$ for all $\rho \in \mathcal{R}_n$. To reverse g , suppose $\lambda \in \mathcal{T}_n$ can be written as $\lambda = \lambda' d \lambda''$, where λ' is of even length and contains at least one square and d is the leftmost domino for which λ can be decomposed in this manner. If no such d exists, then we take $\lambda' = \lambda$. Note that λ' may then be written as $\lambda' = d^\ell s y_1 \cdots y_m s'$ for some $\ell, m \geq 0$, where each y_i is a sequence of two (colored) squares or a single domino and s, s' denote squares (color unspecified). We then reconstruct the initial section $x_0 \rho^{(0)}$ of $g^{-1}(\lambda)$ by letting $x_0 = \delta^{-1}(s s')$ and putting $j_0 = \ell$, $k_0 = m$, and $a_j^{(0)} = \delta^{-1}(y_j)$ for each $1 \leq j \leq m$ in the decomposition of $\rho^{(0)}$ given in (49).

If $\lambda' = \lambda$, then we are done. Otherwise, we repeat the above procedure using the subtiling $d \lambda''$ in place of λ . This yields a second section of $g^{-1}(\lambda)$ of the form in (49) which contains at least one 6 (i.e., $j_1 \geq 1$). We then repeat the procedure until no tiles of λ remain. Note that each section, which we will denote by $x_i \rho^{(i)}$ as before, that is obtained from an iteration of the procedure contains at least one 6, except for possibly the first. Let $\rho = g^{-1}(\lambda)$ be the 6-ary word obtained by concatenating these various sections from left to right in the order they arose. One may verify $\rho \in \mathcal{R}_n$ for all λ and that this procedure defined on λ is indeed the inverse of g . Hence, the mapping g provides the desired bijection between \mathcal{R}_n and \mathcal{T}_n , which completes the proof of (18). Further, it is seen that the number of runs of d in λ wherein the first d in the run starts at an odd position, excluding a possible initial run of d , is always one less than the number of sections $x_i \rho^{(i)}$ in ρ . \square

Note that (1) follows from the well-known fact $|\mathcal{C}_n| = F_{2n}$ for $n \geq 1$, as the right-hand side is seen to enumerate the members of \mathcal{C}_n by considering all possible sequences of multiplicities of the various part sizes. For a bijective proof of an equivalent statement of (1), written as a sum over the compositions of n , see [17, p. 46, Exercise 14f]. We conclude by extending our arguments above to provide a combinatorial explanation of (3).

Proof of (3). Note first that (3) may be written equivalently as

$$2P_{n-1} = \sum_{\beta^* = n} 2^{|\beta|} m_{n-1}(\beta) 1^{\beta_1} 2^{\beta_2} \cdots (n-1)^{\beta_{n-1}}, \quad n \geq 1, \quad (50)$$

where the sum is over all $\beta = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n-1})$ such that $\beta^* = 2\beta_1 + \cdots + n\beta_{n-1} = n$. Equation (50) holds trivially for $n = 1$, so we may assume $n \geq 2$. Recall that \mathcal{C}'_n denotes the subset of \mathcal{C}_n in whose members no part with subscript one is allowed. Let \mathcal{U}_n be the set of ordered pairs (λ, ω) , where $\lambda \in \mathcal{C}'_n$ and ω is a binary word whose length is the number of parts of λ . Then we have that the right side of (50) gives $|\mathcal{U}_n|$ and we seek to show $|\mathcal{U}_n| = 2P_{n-1}$ for $n \geq 2$.

To do so, we describe a recursive construction for obtaining the members of \mathcal{U}_n for $n > 2$ starting with those in $\mathcal{U}_2 = \{(2_2, 0), (2_2, 1)\}$. Consider an $(n - 2)$ -step procedure where, in each step, one of the following five operations is applied to the

final part of λ in $(\lambda, \omega) \in \mathcal{U}_m$ for successively larger $m \in [2, n - 1]$, starting with $m = 2$:

- (1) $a_a \rightarrow (a + 1)_{a+1}, \quad a \geq 2,$
- (2) $a_a \rightarrow (a + 1)_a, \quad a \geq 2,$
- (3²) $c_d \rightarrow (c + 2)_d, \quad 2 \leq d \leq c,$
- (4) $a_b \rightarrow (a - 1)_{b, 2_2},$ and append 0 to $\omega,$
- (5) $a_b \rightarrow (a - 1)_{b, 2_2},$ and append 1 to $\omega,$

where $2 \leq b < a$ in operations (4) and (5). Note that the operation labeled 3² is to count as two steps towards the aforementioned $(n - 2)$ -step procedure, as the size of the final part in λ is increased by two.

In implementing this procedure, the first step must be a 1, 2, or 3², as 4 and 5 require that the current last part of λ be strictly greater than its subscript and we are starting with $\lambda = 2_2$. For the same reason, it is seen that an application of neither 4 nor 5 can directly follow an application of 1, 4, or 5. Similarly, neither 1 nor 2 can follow a 2 or 3², since the application of 1 or 2 requires that the last part of λ be equal to its subscript. It is seen that implementing an $(n - 2)$ -step procedure starting with a member of \mathcal{U}_2 subject to the restrictions discussed above always results in a member of \mathcal{U}_n . Moreover, one can show that each member $(\rho, \delta) \in \mathcal{U}_n$ arises uniquely as all possible $(n - 2)$ -step procedures starting with a member of \mathcal{U}_2 are considered. Note that the number of parts of ρ , i.e., the length of δ , is always one more than the number of times a 4 or 5 is applied during the procedure.

Based on the operations (1)–(5) above and the noted restrictions, we consider a class of 5-ary words wherein each run of 3 is of even length (and hence, where convenient, we will regard a run of 3 of length k as a run of the double-letter 3² of length $k/2$). Let \mathcal{V}_n denote the set of 5-ary words ν of length n satisfying the following properties: (i) each run of 3 in ν is of even length, (ii) ν must start with 1, 2, or 3², (iii) a 1, 4, or 5 not occurring as the final letter of ν must be followed by 1, 2, or 3², (iv) a non-terminal 2 or 3² in ν must be followed by 3², 4, or 5. Note that despite our treating 3² as a single symbol, it counts as two of the n letters of ν . Based on the observations made in the preceding paragraph, we have $|\mathcal{U}_n| = 2|\mathcal{V}_{n-2}$ for $n \geq 2$.

Let \mathcal{P}_n denote the set of Pell tilings of length n where we denote the two kinds of colored squares by b and w , standing for black and white, respectively. Then we have $|\mathcal{P}_n| = P_{n+1}$ for all $n \geq 0$, and so to complete the proof, it suffices to show $|\mathcal{V}_n| = P_{n+1}$.

For this, we define below a bijection between the sets \mathcal{P}_n and \mathcal{V}_n for $n \geq 0$.

Bijection between \mathcal{P}_n and \mathcal{V}_n . The equivalence is trivial if $n = 0$, so we may assume $n \geq 1$. Let $\pi \in \mathcal{P}_n$ be decomposed as

$$\pi = \pi^{(0)} s_1 \pi^{(1)} \dots s_k \pi^{(k)}, \quad k \geq 0, \tag{51}$$

where $\pi^{(0)}, \dots, \pi^{(k)}$ are subtilings and s_1, \dots, s_k are special squares defined as follows. Let s_1 be the leftmost square, if it exists, that directly follows a domino or a black square. If no such square exists, then we take $k = 0$ and $\pi^{(0)} = \pi$. We then define s_i for $i > 1$ inductively by letting s_i be the leftmost square, if it exists, occurring to the right of s_{i-1} and following a domino or square whose color is opposite that of s_{i-1} . This in turn implicitly defines the sections $\pi^{(0)}, \dots, \pi^{(k-1)}$ of π . The section $\pi^{(k)}$ then comprises any remaining tiles of π occurring to the right of the last special square s_k . Note that if $k \geq 1$, then $\pi^{(0)}, \dots, \pi^{(k-1)}$ are each nonempty, with $\pi^{(k)}$ possibly empty.

We now encode π , expressed as in (51), as follows. For each tile in $\pi^{(0)}$, put 1 if w , 2 if b , and 3^2 if d . Then put 4 if s_i is a w and 5 if s_i is a b for each $i \in [k]$. Finally, for each tile in all the sections $\pi^{(i)}$ where $i \geq 1$, put 1 for a square whose color is the same as that of s_i , 2 for a square whose color is opposite that of s_i , and 3^2 for a d . Let π' be the 5-ary word of length n that is obtained after each tile has been encoded as described and the resulting sequence is read from left to right. One may show $\pi' \in \mathcal{V}_n$ by verifying that it satisfies the defining properties (i)–(iv) above. Further, it can be shown that each member of \mathcal{V}_n is represented uniquely as π' for some $\pi \in \mathcal{P}_n$, the details of which we leave to the reader. Thus, the mapping $\pi \mapsto \pi'$ provides the desired bijection between \mathcal{P}_n and \mathcal{V}_n , which completes the proof. \square

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